

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF GENERAL DEVELOPMENT GYMNASTICS

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ABSTRACT

In this article the functions of practical education of the children at the preschool educational institutes, the physical education process, the instant history of the types of gymnastics, the practical suggestions on scientific-theoretical factors of gymnastics classes as well as educational and healthy functions of gymnastics exercises at the preschool educational organizations are identified

Introduction

Preschool education is the main link in continuous education, and teaching children to lead a healthy lifestyle, forming an interest in physical education and sports in students through gymnastics and active games, and raising a physically healthy young generation are among the most important and urgent tasks facing our state. A clear example of this is the fact that the Decree of our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev dated January 24, 2020 No. PF-5924 "On measures to further improve and popularize physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan", dated May 8, 2019 No. PQ-4312-"On the Concept of Developing the Preschool Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", dated February 13, 2019 No. 118 "On the Concept of Developing Physical Education and Mass Sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2023", and dated August 14, 2018 No. PQ-3907 "On measures to raise the spiritual, moral and physical well-being of young people and raise their education and upbringing system to a qualitatively new level" are being consistently implemented today.

The main goal of physical education of children in preschool educational organizations is to form various skills and abilities in children, to develop physical qualities such as strength, agility, speed, agility, endurance, and intelligence.

The tasks of physical education of children in preschool educational organizations:

Task 1. Creating conditions for children to activate goal-directed movements.

Task 2. Formation of important types of movement for life: walking, running, crawling, jumping, crawling, throwing, catching, swimming, riding a bicycle, developing leg, arm, body, and head movements.

Task 3. Alignment and re-alignment. This movement continues from the beginning to the end of the lesson in preschool educational institutions.

Task 4. Expand and deepen game movements, develop physical qualities, agility, dexterity, intelligence, willpower, patience, strength, as well as the ability to keep the body upright.

Task 5. Influence the correct formation of children's physique and prevent flat feet.

Task 6. Cultivate interest in active movement.

Task 7. Provide sufficient imagination and knowledge about the benefits of physical exercises and games, basic hygienic requirements and rules.

The outstanding educator K.D. Ushinsky attached great importance to games, gymnastics, and children's stay in the fresh air. He recommended taking short breaks during gymnastics classes with children to perform exercises that allow them to restore concentration. General developmental gymnastics exercises that make children healthy, strong and have a comprehensive effect on their body, consist of movements performed with individual parts of the body or their combinations. These movements are performed at different speeds and with different muscle tension in the body parts of children. That is why general developmental gymnastics exercises are widely used in preschool educational organizations.

Literature analysis and methodology

In our republic and abroad, issues of physical education of preschool children and gymnastic exercises are discussed: on the theory and methodology of physical education of preschool children T. S. Usmanhodjaev, R. S. Salomov, N. N. Djalilova, on the work on the improvement of health of young children D. D. Sharipova, N. A. Vinogradova, on active games and their implementation R. Azizova, G'. M. Salimov, F. A. Kerimov, S. S. Tajibaev, M. M. Masharipova, T. I. Osokina, M. F. Litvinova, N. T. Lebedeva, V. G. Yakovlev, A. N. Granovsky, L. D. Glazirina, F. G. Frolov on the use of gymnastic games in teaching preschool children various sports, O. Safarov, F. R. Kadirova, Sh. Q. Toshpulatova, M. Z. Fayzullaeva, O. V. Goncharova, R. A. Yuldosheva, A. V. Keneman, D. V. Khukhlaeva, L. V. Kapilevich, V. I. Andreev, D. B. Elkonin, M. E. Vainer, D. I. Gasanova on the influence of games on the mental development of preschool children, E. N. Totskaya, D. V. Mendzheritskaya, L. D. Glazirina, L. I. Penzulaeva, T. A. Semyonova on the development of children's communication, as well as foreign scientists O. P. Bauer, K. Stanbery, G. L. Lendret, August Krog on the influence of large motor skills on the development of children. An analysis of the available literature showed that it is precisely the aspects of developing physical skills and abilities of preschool children through gymnastics that have received little attention in research.

Results

Regular practice of general developmental gymnastics exercises develops, strengthens the muscular, cardiovascular, respiratory, nervous systems and increases the body's working capacity. With their help, almost all physical qualities - strength and endurance, muscle flexibility, coordination of movements and breathing - are developed and improved, and the figure is correctly formed.

General developmental gymnastics exercises are very simple in form and content, and they do not require much time to learn. All participants: young children, preschoolers, schoolchildren, and others can do it.

It is easy to control the physical load when performing general developmental gymnastics exercises. The load depends on the selected exercises and their number in the workout. The level of impact of the exercises is controlled by the following methods:

- number of repetitions
- changing the weight
- changing the method

In order to skillfully conduct general developmental gymnastics exercises for students, a physical education instructor must have the following special knowledge, skills and qualifications:

- be able to master (demonstrate) a large number of gymnastic movements himself;
- clearly know the essence of each movement and why it is used;
- be able to compose a set of movements in accordance with the assigned tasks;
- be able to teach general developmental gymnastics movements in various methods (explanation, demonstration, assignment, game method, etc.) and conduct training;
- master the methods of organizing general developmental gymnastics classes;
- be able to standardize the load depending on the group, age and weight of the participants.

Discussion

In the process of studying the scientific and theoretical foundations of general developmental gymnastics, we studied the following issues and recommended them for discussion:

- In particular, anatomical features are taken as the basis for classifying exercises.

We studied the division of exercises according to the effect on certain parts of the child's body and came to the following conclusions:

1. Exercises for the muscles of the arms and shoulders;
2. Exercises for the muscles of the neck;
3. Exercises for the muscles of the legs and buttocks;
4. Exercises for the muscles of the torso;
5. Exercises for the muscles of the whole body.

In addition to classifying general developmental gymnastics exercises according to their anatomical features, they are also divided according to their physiological effect, that is, according to the development of physical qualities: strength, speed, flexibility, endurance, agility, flexibility. The content of these exercises is bending, writing, stretching, bending, rotation and twisting movements in the joints.

Conclusion

In conclusion, general developmental gymnastic exercises develop the

- muscular,
- cardiovascular,
- respiratory,
- nervous systems of 6-7-year-old children;
- strengthen and increase the body's working capacity.

Physical qualities - strength endurance, muscle flexibility, coordination of movements and breathing are developed and improved during exercise. It is an important factor in the correct formation of children's physique, in their future growth as mentally mature, physically strong and comprehensively healthy

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